

Studies on Adsorption of Molybdate by Precipitated Phosphates of Aluminium(III) and Iron(III) and by Calcium Carbonate

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Manuscript received 1 October 1985, revised 19 September 1986, accepted 3 January 1987

Adsorption of molybdate by precipitated $AlPO_4$, $FePO_4$ and $CaCO_3$ were carried out at 20 and 40° for the Mo-concentration range 0.1–1.0 ppm in solutions of constant ionic strength. The adsorption isotherms were found to follow Langmuir equation. The correlation coefficients for the curves, adsorption maxima and values of constants related to adsorption bonding energy were evaluated. The thermodynamic parameters, such as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were also calculated. The degree of adsorption followed the order, $FePO_4 > AlPO_4 > CaCO_3$.

FORMATION of precipitated $AlPO_4$ and $FePO_4$ is known in soil in the reaction of phosphate with the ions of Fe^{+++} and Al^{+++} in soil solution or in adsorbed phase. Sparingly soluble phosphates of Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} are also the likely products in acid soil on application of phosphatic fertilisers¹. Their chemical nature exhibits some sort of exchange reaction with other anions similar to phosphate. Thus molybdate, similar to phosphate and capable of being associated with it, can go through adsorption or exchange reaction on the precipitated forms of Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} phosphates. Accordingly, adsorption of molybdate on these phosphates as adsorbents has been considered in the present communication. $CaCO_3$ is also an important soil constituent as well as a frequently used soil amendment. The particles of this compound may contribute surface area for anion adsorption. Several authors²⁻⁴ studied the adsorption of phosphate on calcite and described it by Langmuir equation. Accordingly, in the present investigation, precipitated $CaCO_3$ was also taken as an adsorbent for the study on molybdate adsorption.

Being the usual form of the element molybdenum, an essential micronutrient for plants and occurring only in very small amount in soil, adsorption of molybdate by the above adsorbents is considered to be an extremely important subject for investigation. The determination of adsorption isotherm is one of the most useful experimental procedures in the study of the interaction of anions with hydrous oxides or soils. Among the various adsorption equations, the one developed by Langmuir for gas adsorption by solids have been used with some success in solid-liquid (solution) system, even though no rigorous theoretical treat-

ment has been developed for the latter system. The Langmuir equation has been preferred in the present investigation because its parameters have physicochemical significance, representing the extensive (adsorption capacity) and intensive (affinity properties of the adsorbent for the adsorbate (molybdate ions). The equation has been used in the linear form,

$$C/X_m = C/X_m + 1/K \cdot X_m \quad (1)$$

where, C in the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate in solution, K is a constant related to equilibrium constant or bonding energy and X_m is the adsorption maxima.

Standard molar or Gibbs free energy for the adsorption were calculated as

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (2)$$

The standard enthalpy change for adsorption was calculated from the values of K at 20 and 40° by using Vant Hoff equation,

$$\ln \left(\frac{K_1}{K_2} \right) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where, T_1 and T_2 are Kelvin scale temperatures for 20 and 40°, respectively, and K_1 and K_2 the respective constants derived from the Langmuir isotherms. The standard entropy change for adsorption, ΔS° has been calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (4)$$

Experimental

Preparation of $AlPO_4$: Aluminium phosphate or variscite was prepared by mixing dilute solution of $AlCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and NaH_2PO_4 in the mole ratio Al/P=0.4, adjusting pH 4.0 with NaOH solution and digesting at 90° for 14 days. The precipitate

was washed twice with 1% NaCl solution at pH 4.0 to remove adsorbed phosphates and then with 90% ethanol until free from chlorides. The material was finally washed with acetone and dried at 100°^s.

Preparation of iron phosphate: Iron phosphate or strengite was prepared similarly using $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and NaH_2PO_4 solution but adjusting to pH 3.0 and washing the crystallised precipitate first with dilute H_3PO_4 to remove amorphous materials⁵.

Calcium carbonate: Precipitated A.R. grade calcium carbonate was used as adsorbent for the study of molybdate adsorption by this material.

Adsorption methodology: Adsorption studies were conducted by equilibrating the suspension of the above adsorbent materials with appropriate quantities of molybdate, ranging from 0.1 to 1.0 ppm of Mo as molybdic acid (at pH ~6.0) in 50 ml of 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution (to maintain a constant ionic strength) with a solid-solution ratio of 1:50 AlPO_4 and FePO_4 and 1:25 for CaCO_3 , at two constant temperatures 40 and 20°.

Two different sets of suspensions were taken, subjected to reciprocate shaking for 6 h and then kept for 18 h at 20 (± 1) and 40 (± 1)°, respectively, in a B.O.D. incubator. An incubator was used in preference to open thermostatic baths as in the later studies with clays and soil samples B.O.D. incubators were considered to be more appropriate for temperature control. Immediately after incubation the suspensions were filtered through Whatman no. 42 filter paper. After discarding 5-6 ml of the first filtrate, the filtrates were taken for estimating the equilibrium concentration of Mo. The study was conducted in duplicate and the data obtained from the two were found to be more or less concordant. In the filtrate, Mo was determined spectrophotometrically⁶. The amount of Mo adsorbed was calculated by difference from their initial and final concentrations. The adsorption data were fitted to the Langmuir equation and the fit was tested by regression analysis.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption isotherms at 40 and 20° of the precipitated forms of AlPO_4 , FePO_4 and CaCO_3 at various concentrations of molybdates in solution are shown in Fig. 1. The adsorption curves are characterised by gradual rise, followed by flattening of the curves. The adsorption isotherms followed the Langmuir equation. The correlation coefficient values of the Langmuir curves, the Langmuir adsorption maxima, K values related to bonding energy and various thermodynamic constants, calculated thereof, are given in the Table 1. It is observed from the data that FePO_4 adsorbs much higher amount of molybdate than AlPO_4 , which is in conformity with the results obtained in other Al and Fe compounds, where Jones⁷ found higher affinity for Mo or Fe compounds than Al compounds. CaCO_3 , on the other hand, shows a very

little adsorption of molybdate. Adsorption maxima of molybdate for FePO_4 and AlPO_4 adsorbents are found to be higher at lower temperature; on the other hand, CaCO_3 adsorbs a little higher amount of molybdate at higher temperature.

Fig. 1. (A) Molybdate absorption on (a) FePO_4 , (b) AlPO_4 and (c) CaCO_3 at different temperature levels; (B) Langmuir plot of molybdate absorption in (a) FePO_4 , (b) AlPO_4 and (c) CaCO_3 at different temperature levels: (▲) 20° and (●) 40°.

Regarding the K value related to bonding energy, it is observed that in case of FePO_4 , it is much higher than that for AlPO_4 . Though both the adsorbents adsorb higher molybdate at lower temperature, higher strength of adsorption was observed at higher temperature. K value for adsorption of molybdate by CaCO_3 is low, indicating a much weaker strength of adsorption. In this case K value at lower temperature is also higher, unlike for the adsorption of molybdate by FePO_4 and AlPO_4 .

Gibbs free energy change for the adsorption of molybdate on all the three adsorbents are negative, indicating spontaneous nature of adsorption. A higher negative value of ΔG° for adsorption of molybdate on FePO_4 is found. The ΔG° value is always higher at higher temperature level, and increases in the order, $\text{FePO}_4 > \text{AlPO}_4 > \text{CaCO}_3$. The mean ΔH° value for the adsorption is positive in case of AlPO_4 , indicating endothermic nature of adsorption, whereas FePO_4 and CaCO_3 exhibit negative ΔH° values, indicating exothermic nature of adsorption. Regarding the value of mean ΔS° , it is observed that greater positive values for adsorp

TABLE 1—CORRELATION COEFFICIENT VALUES (*r*) OF THE LANGMUIR CURVES, LANGMUIR CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ADSORPTION OF MOLYBDATE BY FePO₄, AlPO₄ AND CaCO₃

Adsorbent	<i>r</i> value*		Adsorption maxima mM g ⁻¹		K value related to equilibrium constant (× 10 ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)		-Δ <i>G</i> ^o kJ mol ⁻¹		Mean Δ <i>H</i> ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	Mean Δ <i>S</i> ^o kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	40°	20°	40°	20°	40°	20°	40°	20°		
FePO ₄	0.953 3	0.953 3	0.555	0.714	923.07	673.67	35.70	34.86	-12.00	0.077
AlPO ₄	0.977 1	0.945 1	0.132	0.153	265.36	199.08	32.48	29.68	+10.91	0.138
CaCO ₃	0.997 1	0.878 9	0.010	0.008	203.29	307.37	31.77	30.72	-15.72	0.103

*Significant at 1% level.

tion of molybdate are shown by CaCO₃, followed by FePO₄ and AlPO₄.

Since precipitated forms of FePO₄ and AlPO₄ contribute large surface area for adsorption, and molybdate and phosphate ions being more or less similar to their behaviour, molybdate ions may be partly exchanged with phosphate on the surface of AlPO₄ and FePO₄. The adsorption on these adsorbents is mostly chemical in nature.

The thermodynamic parameters derived from the study clearly indicate that ferric phosphate obviously exhibits a stronger bonding of molybdate, compared to other adsorbents used in this study. Unlike phosphate, molybdate adsorption on CaCO₃ is not upto the mark or quite significant, though both are anionic in nature. Phosphate is known to be adsorbed by CaCO₃ by chemisorption through precipitation of insoluble calcium phosphate on its surface but molybdate has not been found to behave likewise. The high pH of the CaCO₃ surface appears to inhibit the molybdate anions to be adsor-

bed on it. Unlike phosphate, molybdate also does not react with Ca²⁺ ion readily, mainly due to relatively higher solubility of calcium molybdate compared to that of calcium phosphate.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (D.N.T.).

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